

Value and Moral Adaptability in Improving the Quality of Educational Administration Graduate to Face the Challenges of the Industrial Revolution 4.0

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ABSTRACT: In Indonesia itself, immoral acts, crime, and serious tensions that have occurred recently have made many parents feel sad and worried about their children's mental development and behavior (Kominfo, 2012). Value-oriented education is beneficial in curbing this fissiparous tendency and instilling sentiments of unity and solidarity among people. However, whether we realize it or not, the facts in the field of values education in Indonesia have not yet touched much on empowerment and awareness enlightenment from a global perspective (Primantoro, 2017). On the other hand, value education as a vehicle for awareness of subjective sectarian character values has not yet touched much on universal-objective values (Belen, 2004). Shaping one's character requires the development of traits such as purity, perseverance, faith, sincerity, obedience, fortitude, and humanistic tendencies. Through the educational process, the character is formed, the power of the mind is increased, intelligence is expanded, and a person learns to stand on his own two feet.

KEYWORDS: Value, Moral, Quality of Educational Administration Graduate, Industrial Revolution 4.0

I. INTRODUCTION

We must apply moral values to lead a better personal and social life (Meldiana, 2022). Values are responsible for the development of the individual as a whole because values reflect a person's personality, attitudes, behavior, mission, and vision. Historical facts have shown us enough evidence that the strength and greatness of a nation are essentially based on the power of its character values, which are the backbone for every form of external progress of the government (Mustari, 2011). Moral values can bring peace of mind, a pleasant environment, a better quality of life, sustainability, and harmony in a global society. In this case, education or instilling moral values needs to be adapted to the situations and conditions of each country based on the ideology it adheres to (Primantoro, 2017).

In Indonesia itself, immoral acts, crime, and serious tensions that have occurred recently have made many parents feel sad and worried about their children's mental development and behavior (Kominfo, 2012). Value-oriented education is beneficial in curbing this fissiparous tendency and instilling sentiments of unity and solidarity among people. However, whether we realize it or not, the facts in the field of values education in Indonesia have not yet touched much on empowerment and awareness enlightenment from a global perspective (Primantoro, 2017). On the other hand, value education as a vehicle for awareness of subjective sectarian character values has not yet touched much on universal-objective values (Belen, 2004). Shaping one's character requires the development of traits such as purity, perseverance, faith, sincerity, obedience, fortitude, and humanistic tendencies. Through the educational process, the character is formed, the power of the mind is increased, intelligence is expanded, and a person learns to stand on his own two feet.

Education is an effort to foster and develop human personality in both the spiritual and physical aspects, and not just obtaining certificates and skills has the goal of forming a true Pancasila man based on the Preamble of the 1945 Constitution (Widya, 2019). Education should not only preserve the social heritage but also enrich it. Education being a multipurpose process, not only inculcates social, economic, and cultural awareness in humanity but is also an essential medium for capturing and promoting values that enhance life among human beings. Education is the key to changing the fate of a nation (Kominfo, 2012; Suherman, 2020). Education equips the nation's young generation with a rational and pragmatic approach to life, thus helping people to appreciate life and work for improvement. If proper education is not given, there will be panic and chaos for young people in this country. In creating an ordered life, it is important to have education on values and norms so that young people can understand the values and norms that occur in society (Elwijaya et al., 2021). Values education helps a person to

Value and Moral Adaptability in Improving the Quality of Educational Administration Graduate to Face the Challenges of the Industrial Revolution 4.0

understand, appreciate, and make the right decisions in various personal, family, community, and state problems which are expected to minimize arrogance that often occurs. In other words, value education is the humanization of humans (Windrati, 2017).

Various aspects of civilization, such as population explosion, rapid technological progress, expansion of knowledge, industrialization, globalization, and mobilization, to the influence of various cultures on their own culture, have resulted in society becoming dynamic due to this modernization process. Dynamic Societies tend to experience changes from a physical perspective in the sense of changes involving the type, quantity, and quality of material facilities concerning social and nonphysical interactions (Nasution, 2017). This dynamic society indeed results in various problems of anxiety, stress, and worry in human life. Core human values such as the value of equality as well as obligations and rights, love to love, respect, courage to defend the truth, justice, honesty, tolerance, and cooperation are starting to be affected by crime, poverty, social inequality, caste system, gender inequality, too lousy treatment of women and the elderly (Rianto, 2016). The phenomenon is also exacerbated by the fact that many young people today have lost their moral values due to the new era of commercialization and the modern world.

Therefore, to get around this problem, one needs to see moral or value education as an integral part of the education system. Education without values is not only useless but also very harmful. When social values, morals, and culture.

II. THEORETICAL DESCRIPTION

1. Pancasila values

Pancasila values are the way of life of the Indonesian nation (Herlina, 2011). The values of Pancasila within the Indonesian people are starting to fade over time (Anggraini, 2019). A small example is the third precept value concept which teaches unity, but currently, people are distancing the value of unity and living more individually by enjoying current technological developments (Anggraini et al., 2020). One of the dominating changes in the attitude and character of the Indonesian nation is the development of increasingly modern science and technology in Indonesia. Currently, science and technology are developing rapidly in Indonesia as the era begins to enter the industrial revolution 4.0 (Anggraini et al., 2020). The development of science and technology cannot be separated from cultural and religious values, which can reduce the nation's morale. Foreign cultures began to enter and spread widely in the community, so various kinds of internal and external influences entered the Indonesian nation. With the existence of Pancasila as an ideology, it is hoped that it will strengthen the attitudes and characteristics of society in accepting things outside the limits of norms that exist in Indonesia (Taufik, 2018).

Pancasila is a strong ideology in Indonesia where Pancasila guides community life activities, especially when dealing with people of different ethnicities, races, and religions (Bhagaskoro et al., 2019). Therefore, Pancasila can become a unifying tool for the Indonesian people and a source of value in society, nation, and state (Sofa, 2016). There are three levels of values in Pancasila ideology: fundamental, instrumental, and practical (Agus, 2016). The three values are explained as follows:

- a. Basic value, an abstract and fixed value, regardless of the influence of changes in time. Fundamental values are principles, which are abstract and general, not bound by time and place. The fundamental values of Pancasila grew well from the history of the struggle of the Indonesian people against the colonialists who had brought misery to the Indonesian people, in addition to the ideals of a nation that the colonialists oppressed.
- b. Instrumental values, contextual values. Instrumental values are the elaboration of Pancasila values, which are the direction of performance for a certain period and under certain conditions. Instrumental values can be adapted to the demands of the times. However, the instrument value must refer to the fundamental value described. From its value content, instrumental values are policies, strategies, organizations, systems, plans, programs, and projects that follow these fundamental values. The state institutions authorized to compile instrumental values are the MPR, the President, and the DPR.
- c. The value of praxis, the value contained in everyday life. In the form of how the Indonesian people practice the values of Pancasila. Many practical values manifest the application of Pancasila values, written and unwritten, from the executive, legislative, and judicial branches, by social organizations, economic bodies, community leaders, and even by individual citizens.

Therefore efforts to cultivate self-esteem based on Pancasila must be implemented early. The family and school environment must support cultivating Pancasila attitudes (Anggraini et al., 2020). Small things that can be done quickly are getting used to helping others and getting used to greeting others when meeting others. Because small habits will have a continuous impact if done (Anggraini et al., 2020).

2. Citizenship Values

According to Kellen, values originate from the mind, which encourages and directs human attitudes and behavior (Kealen, 2009; Herlina, 2011; Astuti & Riordan, 2014). In human life, values are used as the basis, reason, or motivation in behaving and behaving whether we realize it or not. Values differ from facts, where facts can be verified empirically, while values are abstract, which humans can understand, think about, and live. Whereas in Latin, the term citizenship is called "civic," then from the word "civic" in English, the word "civic" arises, which means about citizens or citizenship. From the word, "civic" was born the word "civics" Citizenship, Civic Education, and Citizenship Education (Kansil, 2005, p. 3). Civics: the elements of political science or that science

Value and Moral Adaptability in Improving the Quality of Educational Administration Graduate to Face the Challenges of the Industrial Revolution 4.0

dealing with the rights and duties of citizens (Dictionary of education, 1956). From Achmad Sanusi, the following understanding was obtained: civics can be seen as a discipline in political science, so the focus of the study is to exercise rights and obligations according to and within the boundaries of the constitutional provisions of the country concerned (Kansil, 2005: 3, Subadi, 2007). Citizenship values aim to improve the quality of Indonesian people who are virtuous, have a personality, are independent, advanced, demanding, professional, responsible, and productive, as well as physically and mentally healthy. Citizenship values are not only in the form of theory but must provide a moral and social touch.

According to Budi Asnawi, 18 values developed in cultural and national character education are identified from four sources: religion, Pancasila, culture, and moral education goals. The eighteen values in question consist of religion, honesty, tolerance, discipline, hard work, creativity, respect for achievement, friendly or communicative, peace-loving, fondness of reading, environmental care, social care, and responsibility (Asnawi, 2011).

3. Industrial Revolution 4.0

The 4.0 industrial revolution started with the initiative of the German government, which echoed the use of highly computerized technology in manufacturing or manufacturing activities. The German state has a great interest in this matter, and Germany aims to always be at the forefront of the manufacturing world. The word "Industry 4.0" surfaced in 2011 at the Hannover Fair. In 2013, at the same event, a working group was formed led by Siegfried Dais (Robert Bosch GmbH) and Henning Kagermann (German Academy of Sciences and Engineering) (World, 2011). According to Astrid Savitri, industrial revolution 4.0 is the fourth industrial era since the first industrial revolution in the 18th century (Savitri, 2019, 1 & 65). Industrial revolution 4.0 is also known as the fourth industrial revolution (4IR). According to Raymond R. Tjandrawinata, the fourth industrial revolution is built on the third industrial revolution, also known as the digital revolution, which is marked by the proliferation of computers and automation of records in all fields (Tjandrawinata, 2016, p. 39). Furthermore, according to Schwab K, explaining the industrial revolution 4.0 has fundamentally changed human life and work (Schwab, 2017).

III. METHODE

The research design is a literature review or literature review—the method of searching for articles in research journal databases and searching the internet. The database search used was Google Scholar from 2017 to 2022. For article searches, the keywords used were also included in data collection: educational values and morals, quality of undergraduate education, and industrial revolution 4.0. Based on the first search results, hundreds of articles may be found, so it is necessary to have a criterion to homogenize the articles found so that the articles obtained are manageable.

Criteria	Inclusion
Period	Journal articles of the last 5 years
Time	2017 - 2022
subject	Indonesian and English
Journal Type	Values and morals, quality of education, industrial revolution 4.0
Text availability	Original research articles
Period	Full text

The data used in this research is secondary data. Secondary data is data obtained, not from direct observation. This literature review was synthesized using the narrative method by grouping similar extracted data according to the results measured to answer the objectives. Research journals that match the inclusion criteria are then collected. A journal summary is made, including the name of the researcher, year of publication, country of research, the research title, method, and summary of results or findings. The summary of the research journal is in the table containing the title and publication year. The analysis used was journal content analysis, then coding was done on the reviewed journal contents using the psychospiritual category. The data that has been collected is then looked for similarities and differences and then discussed to conclude.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Development of moral values in environmental education in Indonesia

a. What value just developed, e.g. Pancasila values?

Syafruddin Amir, in research entitled _ Pancasila as Integration Philosophy of Education and National Character stated that Pancasila is an ideology nation that must _ be a spirit for every pulse life from society and constitutional activities _ because Pancasila is seen as thinking regarding religion, education, culture, politics, social, and even economy (Amir, 2013). The current era, this one is full of competition with progress technology; the meaning and values of Pancasila must include permanent practice in life for us to exist and not only be made as a symbol solely (Fadhilah, 2019). Potency Pancasila lost existence as ideology on the

Value and Moral Adaptability in Improving the Quality of Educational Administration Graduate to Face the Challenges of the Industrial Revolution 4.0

waves revolution Industry 4.0 can happen if the government as administrators of the state and society in general no work the same for each other and grow awareness about the importance Pancasila values for life together (Faisal, 2019).

b. Citizenship values

Problem values citizenship rated characteristic transformative because felt exists To do an action or implementation process (Haddadi et al., 2017). values _ base citizenship other must _ brought go home through education school is each other respect, understand and value differences and diversity, the creation of a sense of security in a manner dynamic environment for all inroom social specific, like as well as love dear (Koonce, 2018). So, education must remember the seriousness of deep moral decay Public helped with institution education required embedding values of citizenship (Wolhuter et al., 2020).

Value is something valuable, practical, beautiful, and enriching inner (Astuti & Riordan, 2014). Citizenship Education alone is reminiscent education _ of our will, importance, values, rights, and obligations, something citizen order everything to do by the goals and ideals nation and not deviate from what to expect (Antony, 2017). values _ citizenship is intended value _ for increase quality virtuous Indonesian people noble, personality, independent, advanced, challenging, professional, responsible and productive as well as healthy physically and spiritually. Values _ citizenship not only form theory but must give moral and social touch. In a live society, values of citizenship could be applied with the method of always upholding tall tolerance. At the same time, those differences are there so citizens can _ live in harmony and peace and order passed across and obey all existing regulations. _ In life school, grades citizenship could be applied with the method of behaving solemnly in ceremony flag or with following activity school like organization pack bra as form devotion to the state (Antony, 2017).

2. Application of the moral value of education in the environment work company national and inter-company

Inside _ a company, usually made standard or internal moral code form code of ethics or the usual called with code of conduct. A Code of conduct this written formally and relatedly to various rules, standards, and systems, incl with ethics business (Djajendra, 2017). A moral code or code of ethics is meant to illuminate the work process, so everyone knows what is allowed and what cannot be done on the spot work. Applying moral values in place position could help save the management _ company from the damage done by the behaviour of no human ethical company (Djajendra, 2017).

Application of moral values is one _ key to success happening work cooperation, communication, coordination, and collaboration in place work (Djajendra, 2017). Morality must Become behaviour, choice, life, personality and character that can be displayed in connection to work every day. In this, the application of personal moral values must adapt self with moral values created by the company. Suppose more discreet employees prioritize moral values of what they believe outside _ the belief company. In that case, a conflict will occur that results in the loss of destination morality expected by the company (Djajendra, 2017).

As for form application educational, moral values that must be noticed in environment work good company national nor company international among them like do not too often come too late, do not like talk about the ugliness of others, guard attitude do not laugh and talking too hard, take care cleanliness environment work and each other value to superior nor to fellow employees (Wulansari, 2021). There are also times currently communicate; we could apply several rule ethics, like each other stare eye moment talk, listening to opponents talk to each other, understanding moments speak, avoiding disturbing others, remembering others' rights to talk, focusing on the problem and not interrupting others moments currently say (Wulansari, 2021). Applying moral and ethical values in place such work _ shape will help increase the character of society, as well could understand what is good and what is not good with insight.

3. Challenge revolution industry 4.0

Revolution Industry 4.0 fundamentally resulted in _ a change method man thinks, lives, and relates with others (Prasetyo & Trisyanti, 2018). this era has disrupted various activities in many fields, not only in the field of technology but also in other areas such as economics, society, and politics. In field technology, the implementation of revolution Industry 4.0 can be seen and felt from exists invention Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence, sophisticated robots, autonomous vehicles, computing cloud, big data, realistic simulation, 3D printing, blockchain, nanomaterials and digital twins. The sector economy has seen how sector service transportation from online and motorcycle taxis (Prasetyo & Trisyanti, 2018). The same thing happened in the fields, social and political. Interaction becomes social _ without limit (unlimited) because of the convenience of Internet access and technology. The same happened in field politics; through convenient digital access, political action could be collected based on politically specific ideologies through movements and social media.

However, behind _ the conveniences offered, especially character _ technical, organizational, and economical, many believe that Revolution Industry 4.0 saves various threats in the form of (1) increased unemployment, (2) existence stratification social, (3) existence threat to cyber security, (4) breach privacy, ethical and social, norms, (5) existence threat war based on discoveries new and developing divisions of the world into developed and developing countries (Rymarczyk, 2020). Furthermore, Irianto also simplifies challenge industry 4.0 into several parts such as (1) readiness industry ; (2) power work trusted ; (3) convenience Settings social culture; and (4) diversification and creation fieldwork (Irianto, 2017). Sung also identified challenges in industry 4.0 as

Value and Moral Adaptability in Improving the Quality of Educational Administration Graduate to Face the Challenges of the Industrial Revolution 4.0

follows: (1) increasing problem security technology information, (2) reliability and stability machine production, (3) lack of adequate skills, (4) reluctance for change by the stakeholder's interests, and (5) loss many profession because changed Becomes automation (Sung, 2017).

4. Answer challenge revolution 4.0

Future and generations _ moments will depend on how we can now prepare ourselves for the challenges of the Revolution Industry 4.0 and reduce incoming threats (Rymarczyk, 2020). Industry 4.0 is not only about technology and processes, including cyber-physical systems, the Internet of Things (IoT), Internet of Service (IoS), but also about the method of work and the new roles of the employee in the industry (Alcacer & Machado, 2019). They are resolving challenges related to Industry 4.0, improving engagement and training entrepreneurs and employees. This _ especially applies to education in print and keeping quality source power humans (Gajek et al., 2022). So from that is, formation participant, educate in learning in revolution Industry 4.0 of the 21st century must also adjust for results learning could give Skills to student namely 4C which includes : (1) communication, (2) collaboration, (3) thinking critically and problem-solving, and (4) creative and innovative (Wena, 2020). Besides it, according to Fadilah (2019), challenges and reinforcement of Pancasila ideology in face revolution Industry 4.0 are:

Grounding Pancasila in development revolution 4.0 with method increase Pancasila understanding, reduce exclusivism social, reduces gap social, improves Pancasila insight for state officials, and makes Pancasila exemplary in face revolution industry 4.0.

Strengthening Pancasila in the face revolution Industry 4.0 is with increased source power superior Indonesian people by Pancasila values.

Defend the existence of Pancasila as Indonesian State Ideology.

Next, according to Director Requirements Work, S. Junaedah moment representing the Minister of Manpower of the Republic of Indonesia on the agenda of the 1st Brotherhood National Conference Lecturer The title of the Republic of Indonesia at the Nusantara 1 Building, DPR RI, Jakarta, Friday (26/10/2018) . that at least There are three possible strategies used for answer challenge revolution Industry 4.0, among others namely : (1) Ministry of Manpower map transformation industry, setup profession as well as future skills, and planning power work with the perpetrators business and industry in each sector priority, (2) government massive training work and certification framed profession _ in triple policy skilling, that is skilling, up-skilling, and re-skilling, and (3) the government also equips Indonesian human resources with soft skills, entrepreneurship and digital skills (disnakertrans.kalteng.go.id, 2018).

5. What values and morals are required for a graduate of Education Administration/management education in the labour market in the revolutionary era industry 4.0

To follow the development with _ well, needed moral values or moral values that consist of kindness, respect, caring, and beneficial tolerance for nature and humanity (Larasati, 2022). Necessary values and morals in facing the labour market in the era of revolution Industry 4.0 are to have good character. _ In this, the surface is typical values _ well, that is knowing score goodness, will do well, for real alive good, and impactful good to embedded environment _ in yourself and reflected in behaviour (Permana, 2022).

Kindly coherent character radiating from results through think, work, heart, sports, tastes and intentions of somebody or a group of people (Larasati, 2022). The character could be individual (personal and constituted innate from born), social (construction social), and Mondial (universal symbols that are inherited from various inherent principles _ in general). According to Larasati, a surface is a wise person _ namely logical, ethical, aesthetic, and religious (Larasati, 2022). If split again, character logic consists of other characteristics like critical, innovative, systematic, comprehensive, reflective, and radical (Permana, 2022). Then character ethics consists of awareness, freedom, and responsibility answer. Then character aesthetics could be rated outwardly and inwardly (Permana, 2022). Temporary character religions must mirror the attitude of each other values to adherents of other faiths (Larasati, 2022).

6. How a management education graduate is absorbed in the work world moment this. (a lot and quality / not a lot and quality / a lot no quality / no many no quality)

The world of work in the era of revolution Industry 4.0 will start to understand or have hope special about competent undergraduates who will become employees 4.0, i.e. with proof that they have appropriate skills. _ It is what will become hope new good for the company nor able employees _ called company 4.0 and employees 4.0. Employee 4.0 is an individual who has adapted to the digital work environment (Lee et al., 2019).

7. How Pancasila values and citizenship support facility power work in the industrial era 4.0

Development education in the Revolution Industry 4.0 moment this be marked with happening. Significant changes in knowledge, technology, and communication influence people's character and the work world (Maemunah, 2018; Trisiana et al., 2019; Nasution, 2017.; Normah et al., 2020). This time also will occur changes from the previous era, so the impact logical must _ face changes and shifts in the type of power work in the present and future generations (Suwardana, 2018). Indonesia, as a developing country, participates committed in this era also have to be capable of preparing source power, reliable man, have _ good discipline, and have

Value and Moral Adaptability in Improving the Quality of Educational Administration Graduate to Face the Challenges of the Industrial Revolution 4.0

high quality and quantity to be capable of competing in the era of global competition (Subekti et al., 2018). However, in Indonesia, when still faced with conditions Source Power Human (HR) with force work around 58.76% which elementary school and junior high school graduates and problems incompatibility reached 63% because that needed something effort from as early as possible in effort development of human resources so that skills and competencies source power people in Indonesia can compete (Kusdiartini, 2018); (Revolution Industry 4.0 And Its Importance Development Quality Source Power Human (HR) Indonesia, 2019). it shows that circumstances source power people in Indonesia are still low and far from productive. Whereas should source power humans in this era must more capable compete and more good from before. Condition education in the revolutionary era industry moment this like like two side currency. One side has scored positive for productivity results work and production process efficiency. However, on the other hand, the revolution industry also has a negative side; among others is the competitive world of work much power work is not used and disrupted must technology anticipated by Indonesia (Satya, 2018). Change This also impacts the development of the world, which is entering the digital era called the era of disruption. All sectors, including politics, economics, and education, also feel the impact (Harto, 2018). Impact the lead to the world of education as means for implementation and distribution of knowledge in an explicit must-have system that can support implementation activity. It could be seen from the accompanying challenges faced by education in Indonesia that it is required to have a method, think of a way to learn, and know how to act, but the participants still teach limited. Because it is necessary exists effort from early by educators to produce quality education and improve the morale of the generation gold in the future come (Nursyifa, 2019). The influence of fast technology and communication in the era of disruption also affects the height of the use of social media by the community (Triyanto & Fadhillah, 2018). it showed that social media now the more mushroomed, so raises anti-social behaviour and dissolving habits well-rooted from Pancasila values among the Public, especially students (Amedia, 2015; Nasihuddin, 2016), not yet again happening inequality Among ideal expected moral attitudes with circumstances actually about circumstances social events at school as well as in society. It signifies the need to improve and strengthen Pancasila values in the educational process carried out through life processes in the community, nation and state.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Revolution-era industry 4.0 moment need power work graduate or undergraduate with the ability to data literacy, technology and people. Data literacy is required to increase skills and analyse big data for interest enhancement service public and businesses. Next, literacy technology is needed to improve processing digital data and information skills. At the same time, literacy man Required to be mastered because showing soft element skills can help collaborate, adapt and become wise in the era of a "flood" of information. In thing, this, role values and morals that develop in Indonesia can support fulfilment power religious work, honesty, tolerance, discipline, work challenge, creativity, respect for achievements, friends or communication, love peace, love reading, caring environment, care social, and responsibility answer. Achievements learning bachelor administration education in a manner general has to Fulfil contained values in Pancasila and citizenship that is capable manage institution education with prioritize values and qualities education, efficiency, effectiveness, justice, and democracy good individually or team. However, more is needed to Fulfil the challenge of revolution industry 4.0. Bachelor administration education needs to have an attitude consistent with adaptability values and morals, capable of facing challenges and threats posed by the revolution industry 4.0 and even society 5.0.

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Value and Moral Adaptability in Improving the Quality of Educational Administration Graduate to Face the Challenges of the Industrial Revolution 4.0

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